

NEW MANUFACTURING TECHNIQUE OF HEAT-INSULATING WOOD FOAM WITHOUT PLASTICS

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ABSTRACT: The paper is a contribution of authors to the knowledge enrichment on the recent development of the new manufacturing technique of wood foam for packaging excluding plastics in its preparation mixture. Given that there is only one industrial manufacturer in the world of this type of wood foam with excellent heat-insulating properties, the current work presents an original method of its production using raw materials different from those applied in the industrial manufacturing recipe. Oak and beech wood waste, bentonite clay as a nanomaterial, calcium lignosulfonate as a surfactant, and distilled water were materials chosen by authors. The features of the new optimal product were density of 0.06 g-cm⁻³, heat conductivity of 0.027 W·m⁻¹·K⁻¹, porosity of 94.1 %, and compression strength of 985 kPa, being approximately similar by comparison with industrial products.

KEYWORDS: wood foam, plastic, bentonite clay, calcium lignosulfonate, packaging.

1 INTRODUCTION

The heat-insulating materials commonly used in building construction are materials based on polymers (plastic materials). Their effectiveness in the isolation process has already been proven, but under the current conditions, characterized by the special care towards environmental protection, their use is considered inadequate for two main reasons: the possible affecting the human health and difficulty of recycling this material type at the end of operating cycle (Ferreira et al., 2023).

Replacing plastics with ecological materials without influencing the valuable properties of polymer-based thermal insulators by adding bio-materials or natural feedstocks represent interesting solutions (Ferreira et al., 2023).

Insulating materials prepared from wood (such as wood fiber) are known and partly used in present, but the dimensional stability is less satisfactory compared to that of polymer-based products. Also, thermal performances are inferior to those of plastic-based materials (Insulation materials, 2000).

Wood foam represents a recent concern of researchers in the field of thermal insulation. Currently, the Fraunhofer Institute (Germany) is testing the production of a wood foam as an

advanced material with special thermal insulation properties (Wood, 2023). The recipe for its manufacture is grinding the wood waste in the presence of high proportion of deionized water until the suspension is formed. This is chemically foamed with an adequate surfactant and then dried and hardened into a moisture-free room. Using a beech wood, the German researchers obtained extremely light foam with porous structure having the density between 0.04-0.28 g-cm⁻³.

Traders' interest in the use of wood foam packaging manufactured under environmentally friendly conditions by excluding traditional plastic materials from its composition has increased in recent years (Fofana, 2024).

According to (Alava & Koivisto, 2021), researchers from Aalto University in Finland obtained foam resistant to mechanical stress and heat starting from a mix of lignin, wood fibers, and nanoclay, avoiding the use of plastic. Lignin is included in the wooden structure together with cellulose and hemicellulose. It is a polymer in amorphous state and fulfills the role of binder or matrix. Lignin has the peculiarity of a highly branched three-dimensional structure (Wood composition, 2022). Wood fibers are usually cellulosic elements extracted from trees and applied

to produce several materials such as paper, cardboard, tissue, etc. Wood chips originating from trunk wood are transformed in wood fiber at high mechanical pressure and high temperature. Nanoclays are nanoparticles of layered mineral silicates. Depending on the chemical composition and morphology of nanoparticles, nanoclays are grouped into several classes such as montmorillonite/smectite, kaolinite, hectorite, bentonite, and halloysite. Montmorillonite/smectite in the form of extremely thin alumina-silicate plates (about 1 nm) forming multilayer stacks of about 10 μm is the most commonly used nanoclay, being applied in the experiment at Aalto University. The foam produced in this way is biodegradable and cheap, being intended for use as packaging, but the field of applicability can also be extended for insulation in construction, being resistant to water and fire.

Currently, only one type of wood foam packaging called "Fibrease" manufactured by Stora Enso Oyj Company in Finland and Sweden is commercially available in the world (Fibrease, 2024; Coombes, 2024). The basic raw material is durable Nordic wood (such as European oak, pine, European larch, etc.), which has excellent damping, crushing, and insulation properties. Post-consumer packaging can be easily recycled and this is an important quality compared to similar polymer-based materials.

According to (Coombes, 2024), the advantages of using wood foam as packaging are: using renewable resources, significant reduction of plastic pollution, commercial appearance, protection in transit, facilitating recycling after use.

Fibu AB Hallstahammar is another Swedish company involved in the production of renewable, biodegradable wood fiber foam, whose objective is to reduce plastic pollution in the fields of packaging, construction, and furniture manufacturing (Biodegradable, 2023). According to Fibu company estimates, 59 % of the European Union's annual waste is packaging, 40 % of plastic requirements being directed towards packaging operations. The wood fiber foam of the Swedish company is considered to be fully renewable, biodegradable and recyclable.

The current paper presented below includes results of the Romanian research team's concern for designing an internationally competitive wooden foam for packaging. The originality of the work consists in the choice of other material types for the starting mixture compared to those reported in the literature by researchers from Stora Enso Oyj, the main industrial producer of wood foam for packaging.

The previous experience of the Romanian research team in the field of wood foam production (through the wood delignification process) was gained following this research (Paunescu et al., 2023), in which the made wood foam had a density of 0.024 $\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, heat conductivity of 0.031 $\text{W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$, and compressive strength of 900 kPa.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

The materials that composed the starting mixture for the production of wood foam intended for packaging were: a ground mixture of oak and beech wood in the form of sawdust, bentonite clay, and calcium lignosulfonate (LSC) as a surfactant.

The wood waste was recycled from a Romanian wood processing workshop. The wood sawdust was finely ground in a ball mill and then sieved, the particle sizes less than 100 μm being selected.

Bentonite clay is a natural clay with fine and soft texture forming a paste by mixing with water. This paste can be also utilized for medical or cosmetic purposes. Bentonite clay contains natural minerals such as calcium, magnesium and iron, providing additional benefits (Bentonite clay, 2023).

Fluidizing additives are surface-active substances, that introduced in low proportions into the material mixture cause its fluidization. Their influence is the adsorption on the surface of solid particles, determining phenomena such as dispersion, hydration, and forming the strength structure. The main surfactants industrially used are lignosulfonates due to their high fluidizing action and low cost because they are obtained as industrial by-products. Calcium lignosulfonate (LSC) extracted from sulfite paste during the pulp manufacturing and commercially available as a water-soluble fine powder was chosen for use in this experiment. LSC is a polymer with three-dimensional structure and high molecular mass (Moldovan, 1978; Ouyang et al., 2006).

2.2 Methods

The adopted preparation method included first the grinding of oak and beech wood waste in pre-wetting conditions in a knife-grinding laboratory equipment. The surfactant (calcium lignosulfonate) was added over the wood ground (having the particle size below 400 μm) in very low weight proportions, reducing the surface tension of the suspension and facilitating the formation of foam. Also, bentonite clay as the chosen nanoclay was

introduced into this wetted mixture including distilled water. The three components of this mixture were homogenized by mechanical stirring. The suspension concentration was not higher than 20 % (i.e. 20 % solids and 80 % distilled water). The suspension foaming was carried out in an electrically operated device by stirring at 8000 rpm for 10 min, observing the volume occupied by the growing foam until its stabilization. The stabilized wet foam was loaded into rectangular metal moulds. The subsequent drying in an electric laboratory oven at 75 °C for 8 hours led to obtaining the final hardened form of the wood foam.

2.3 Investigation methods for determining the specimen features

The investigation methods utilized in this work are usually used in research activities. Archimedes' principle was the method applied for measuring the apparent density of wood foam specimens. Using ASTM C642-97, the apparent porosity was determined by dividing the difference between wet and dry weight by the difference between wet weight and suspended weight of the sample. Heat conductivity was measured at room temperature using the HFM448 Lambda heat-flow-meter (SR EN 1946-3:2004). Identifying the compression strength was performed using a universal testing machine. The specimens were compressed at 1.4 mm·min⁻¹ (ASTM D695) and the compressive strength was determined at 10 % compression (ASTM D1621-16). The microstructural appearance of foams could be analyzed with the Biological Microscope MT5000 model, 1000 x magnification. Water uptake was measured by maintaining wood foam samples in humidity chamber at 85 % humidity for 30 days according to ASTM C272/C272M-18.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Results

The results analysis was carried out after testing the four experimental variants prepared according to the method described above, whose composition is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Composition of the experimental variants

Compositio n	Variant 1	Variant 2	Variant 3	Variant 4
Oak and beech wood (g)	48.9	48.4	47.9	47.4
Bentonite clay (g)	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5
Surfactant LSC (mg)	75	100	125	150
Distilled water (g)	200	200	200	200
Wet suspension (g)	250	250	250	250

According to the data in Table 1, the design of the starting mixture included 20 % solid materials (wood, nanoclay, and LSC surfactant) and the remaining 80 % distilled water, so that the wet suspension had the constant value of 250 g. Using low proportions of bentonite clay (between 2-5 % from the solid amount) and much low proportions of calcium lignosulfonate LSC (in the range of 0.15-0.30 % from the solids) resulted amounts of nanoclay between 1-2.5 g and respectively, LSC within the limits of 75-150 mg distributed evenly increasing in the four experimental variants.

The physical, thermal, mechanical and microstructural characteristics of the wood foam specimens are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Characteristics of wood foam specimens

Characteristic	Var. 1	Var. 2	Var. 3	Var. 4
Apparent density (g·cm ⁻³)	0.15	0.11	0.09	0.06
Apparent porosity (%)	90.0	92.1	93.0	94.1
Heat conductivity (W·m ⁻¹ ·K ⁻¹)	0.038	0.033	0.029	0.027
Compression strength (kPa)	818	820	959	985
Water uptake (wt. %)	5.6	5.0	4.1	4.2
Pore size (µm)	22-38	30-72	45-75	40-98

Images of physical aspect of the four wood foam specimens obtained by preparation recipes mentioned above are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Aspect of wood foam specimens
a – specimen 1; b – specimen 2; c – specimen 3;
d – specimen 4.

Investigating the experimental results included in Table 2, it is noted the special heat-insulating properties of specimens, in particular, those corresponding to samples 3 and 4, in which the weight proportions of nanoclay and calcium lignosulfonate (LSC) in the material mixture are increasing (2-2.5 g for bentonite clay and respectively, 125-150 mg for LSC). Thus, apparent density decreased below $0.1 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, heat conductivity also decreased under $0.03 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$, and apparent porosity increased up to 93-94.1 %. The use in making recipe of nanomaterials (bentonite clay) favoured keeping the compression strength value to an acceptable level (959-985 kPa) for an extremely porous and light material type. The cell size in the wood foam specimen structure was under $100 \mu\text{m}$, being reached the highest range (between $40\text{-}98 \mu\text{m}$) in the case of the specimen corresponding to variant 4. The water-absorbing level after the moisture absorption test was within normal limits for this material type (in the range of 4.1-5.6 wt. %).

The microstructural appearance of wood foam specimens is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Microstructural appearance of wood foam specimens
a – specimen 1; b – specimen 2; c – specimen 3;
d – specimen 4.

According to the pictures in Fig. 2, the microstructural homogeneity of samples is obvious. The cells size range is those included in Table 2.

3.2 Discussion

Starting from the middle of the 20th century, as a result of the flammability standards issued, flame retardant substances were added to foams and plastics, without the potential negative influences on human health and the environment being known.

Recent research on these aspects has shown that exposure to halogenated flame retardants, as in the case of wooden furniture foam, leads to unwanted health effects. On the other hand, when these products reach the end of their life, their simple elimination is not enough, complex methods being necessary to avoid the risks for environmental caused by the storage of these wastes in landfills (Lucas et al., 2018).

The interest in the production of wood foams is continuously increasing in recent years, the Fraunhofer Institute for Wood Research in Germany being the most important research center in the field.

In particular, the manufacture of wood foam packaging is also in full development recently through the research carried out by Aalto University in Finland.

Both mentioned European institutions have as their objective the elimination of plastics from the mixture composition prepared for the production of foam.

The authors of the current work aimed at the production of wood foam packaging, simultaneously using two types of wood waste (oak and beech) mixed in approximately equal weight proportions.

Unlike the recipe adopted by (Alava & Koivisto, 2021) which included in the starting mixture lignin extracted from the wooden structure, in the current experiment, commercially available calcium lignosulfonate was used as a surfactant.

Also, nanomaterials of the nanoclay type were used in the experiment. Unlike montmorillonite/smectite adopted from the known nanoclays by Stora Enso Oyj, in the experimental recipe bentonite clay containing natural minerals (Ca, Mg, Fe) was chosen, usually used for medical or cosmetic purposes.

The four tested experimental variants have highlighted excellent heat-insulating properties of all wood foam specimens. The overall analysis of the physical, thermal, mechanical, and microstructural features of specimens at the end of the manufacturing process allowed the choice of variant 4 as the optimal option. Thus, the lowest values of apparent density ($0.06 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$) and heat conductivity ($0.027 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$) as well as the highest value of apparent porosity (94.1 %) were reached, indicating insulating properties at the level of industrially obtained products. Also, the microstructural aspect of the optimal sample shows the homogeneity of the distribution of closed cells with sizes between 40-98 μm . The water uptake is at a low level (4.2 wt. %) typical for this wooden material.

4 CONCLUDING REMARKS

The objective of the work is to create a wood foam packaging using oak and beech wood together and avoiding plastic materials. Since the introduction of plastics into the mix of materials has been identified as being responsible for affecting human health and the extremely difficult recycling at the end of the life cycle of these materials, in recent years the concern of researchers for the manufacture of environmentally friendly wooden products has intensified. The current work aims to contribute to this international effort.

The originality of this work consists in the adoption of different materials that compose the starting mixture compared to those industrially used by Stora Enso Oyj, the only manufacturer in the world. Except for the completely different type of wood waste, the other components of the mixture were also replaced: calcium lignosulfonate instead of lignin and bentonite clay instead of montmorillonite/smectite clay having the role of surfactant and nanoclay, respectively.

The experimental results showed adequate heat-insulating properties of wood foams. The variant considered optimal reached the lowest values of apparent density ($0.06 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$) and thermal conductivity ($0.027 \text{ W}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{K}^{-1}$), while porosity reached the highest value (94.1 %). The results regarding these thermal properties were almost similar to those of industrial products. In microstructural terms, the distribution homogeneity of the cells that make up the matrix of the optimal product was very good, their size range being within the limits of 40-98 nm. Also, the water absorption of the optimal sample was low (4.2 wt. %) corresponding to the specific level of the wood material.

By using materials different from those adopted in the world (Fibrease, 2024), the work constitutes a contribution of authors to the new manufacturing technique of wood foam packaging, excluding the use of plastics in this process. The continuation of similar scientific investigations of the authors' team is the own objective for future research.

5 REFERENCES

- Alava, M., Koivisto, J. (2021). Wood-based foam to replace Styrofoam and other plastics, Forest bioeconomy future catalogue climate change, Aalto University, Espoo, Finland, available at: <https://forest.fi/products-services/wood-based-foam-to-replace-styrofoam-and-other-plastics/#1f63a433> Accessed: 2024-02-12.
- Bentonite clay: 11 benefits and uses (2023). Medical News Today, available at:

<https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/325241> Accessed: 2024-02-13.

Biodegradable wood fibre packaging foam from Fibu to be distributed worldwide. (2023), available at:

<https://packagingeurope.com/news/biodegradable-wood-fibre-packaging-foam-from-fibu-to-be-distributed-worldwide/9700.article> Accessed: 2024-01-22.

Coombes, R. (2024). Wood foam packaging-what is it, and should you be using it? Environment/Guides and Advice, GWP Group, Cricklade, Wiltshire, UK, available at: <https://www.gwp.co.uk/guides/wood-foam-packaging/> Accessed: 2024-03-11.

Ferreira, E.S., Dobrzanski, E., Tiwary, P., Agrawal, P., Chen, R., Cranston, E.D. (2023). Insulative wood materials templated by wet foams, *Materials Advances*, Royal Society of Chemistry, vol. 4, pp. 641-650, available at: <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2MA00852A> Accessed: 2022-11-07.

Fibrease-A sustainable wood foam, Stora Enso Oyj Company, available at:

<https://www.storaenso.com/en/products/bio-based-materials/wood-foam-by-stora-enso/fibrease> Accessed: 2024-03-10.

Fofana. O. (2023). Is wood foam packaging right for your business? available at: <https://www.packaging-gateway.com/features/is-wood-foam-packaging-right-for-your-business/> Accessed: 2024-01-10. Wood

Lucas, D, Petty, S.M., Keen, O., Luedeka, B., Schlummer, M., Weber, R., Barlaz, M., Yazdani,

R., Riise, B., Rhodes, J., Nightingale, D., Diamond, M.L., Vijgen, J., Lindeman, A., Blum, A., Kashland, C.P. (2018). Method of responsibly managing end-of-life foams and plastics containing flame retardants: Part 1. *Environmental Engineering Science*, vol. 35, no. 6, pp. 573-587, available at: <https://doi.org/10.1089/ees.2017.0147>. Accessed: 2024-02-25.

Moldovan, V. (1978). Aditivi in betoane, Editura Tehnica, Bucuresti, pp. 130-157.

Ouyang, X., Qiu, X., Chen, P. (2006). Physicochemical characterization of calcium lignosulfonate-A potentially useful water reducer, *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspect*, Elsevier, vol. 282-283, pp. 489-497, available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2005.12.020> Accessed: 2018-09-22.

Paunescu, L., Volceanov, E., Paunescu, B.V. (2023). New wood foam-heat insulating material obtained through oak wood-delignification process, *Nonconventional Technologies Review*, vol. 27, no. 4, pp. 12-16, available at: <https://www.revtn.ro/index.php/revtn> Accessed: 2024-01-26.

Wood-From tree to foam. (2023). Fraunhofer Institute for Wood Research, Braunschweig, Germany, available at: <https://www.fraunhofer.de/en/institutes.htm> Accessed: 2024-02-29.